

ORGANIZATIONAL PROCESS OF ARTISTIC AMATEUR CIRCLES

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Abstract. This article talks about the development of folk art and artistic amateur art, identifying talented young people, and supporting creative young people.

Key words: folk art, talented youth, Nizam, tugarak, studio, festival, pageant. Shashmaqom, teahouse, dance, initiative, art groups, seminar, competition, national value, tradition, intangible cultural heritage.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС КРУЖКОВ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ САМОДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о развитии народного творчества и художественной самодеятельности, выявлении талантливой молодежи, поддержке творческой молодежи.

Ключевые слова: народное творчество, талантливая молодежь, низам, тугарак, студия, фестиваль, театрализованное представление. Шахмаком, чайхана, танец, инициатива, творческие коллективы, семинар, конкурс, национальная ценность, традиция, нематериальное культурное наследие.

The center is established in order to study and meet the needs of the public in the preservation and study of national traditional culture, to support artistic creativity, other amateur creative initiatives and socio-cultural activity of the population, and to organize its recreation.

It is possible to develop artistic creativity and applied art by preserving and increasing objects of the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan, by organizing modern studios and circles, as well as artistic amateur groups.

Along with the organization of artistic communities, the wide spread of modern cultural and educational services required by all levels of the population, the organization of Internet studios, electronic resources, including information and communication technologies and foreign language courses through the Internet, many organization of interesting and entertaining shows and other solemn events, discussion clubs and competitions in intellectual games in function halls, is the basis of attracting people to cultural centers. Because it is clear that anyone who has visited a show or an event will be familiar with the schedule of the cultural center. From this it follows that the person who came is definitely interested in a single child and will inevitably bring his children.

Amateur artistic and practical groups, studios and circles, folk theaters, cultural-knowledge, history-local studies, scientific-technical, natural-ecological, cultural-household, collection-gathering interests and other interests organization of philharmonics, amateur associations and clubs and organization of their work is the basis for creation of paid clubs in addition to the budget clubs of the cultural center.

Creating a database on genres of folk art, intangible cultural heritage and developing amateur art, improving the skills of the center's specialists, establishing a system of permanent exhibitions, studios, master classes, seminars, artistic teams in the cultural center creates a factor of many abandonments and attraction of population.

In the relevant Resolution of the President dated 28.11.2018, it was specifically focused on the establishment of cultural centers, the organization of republican competitions on various topics, and the establishment of artistic teams. In addition to improving the quality of paid cultural services and providing meaningful free time for the population, a number of tasks have been defined in the cultural and public recreation centers. In particular, centers are tasked with organizing the following: organization of artistic and practical creative teams, amateur groups,

Courses on "Speech culture", attracting children to clubs and learning foreign languages, organizing contests, festivals of folk art and performing arts, public holidays, shows and folk entertainments.

Many artists have grown up among the participants of artistic amateur clubs and teams organized in cultural centers. Also, singing and dancing, folklore, vocal-variety, status, askiya, curiosity, trumpet-trumpet, bacchanal, doormanship, circus, national instruments, visual and applied arts, folk theater and puppet theaters. The examination is being held according to the directions and at the festivals, talents whose names are not yet known to many people are identified, and positive work is being done to widely promote their creations.

Broad coverage of the programs of cultural centers prepared and conducted by artistic teams, i.e. auditions, festivals and creative evenings, concert programs and cultural and educational promotion meetings held on the relevant TV and radio channels of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan. and preparing teams for competitions organized on the topics of "Ancient Earth Tones", "Bakhshiyona", "Eternal Voices", "Mother Earth Tones", "Field Performance Art", "Folk Oral Art" is our main goal. it should be our duty.

In the process of getting to know artistic teams in cultural and recreational centers, printing and distributing the necessary educational and methodical manuals, collections, recommendations and other handouts for leaders and employees of cultural centers, clubs, studios and artistic amateur teams. we need to start breeding.

However, it should be noted that the selection of unsuitable buildings for the organization of cultural and public recreation centers, the lack of auditoriums in some centers to ensure the cultural needs of the population, and to increase the types and quality of cultural services based on the requirements of the times, the existence of financial problems in repairing and equipping them based on the established standard requirements, the lack of highly educated personnel in the field, the lack of necessary conditions for local specialist personnel, the insufficiency of regulatory legal documents on the organization of the activities of cultural centers, the heads of the centers and the lack of development of assessment criteria aimed at improving the work efficiency of employees, the fact that the salary payment procedure for employees was developed in 1996, the lack of study of foreign experiences and the lack of close creative cooperation with them are considered to be urgent problems in the field and require their solution is waiting.

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